

COST BENEFIT ANALYSIS OF HOUSEHOLDS ENERGY BOXES DEPLOYMENT IN EUROPE: IMPACT OF THE SPOT PRICES.

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ABSTRACT

The present paper presents a study willing to assess the profitability of replacing a conventional thermostat by a Smart Thermostat – also called Energy Boxes – in electrically heated households. It assumes that such replacement is a prerequisite for a dweller to take the entire advantage of a subscription at Real Time Price (RTP) tariffs. A deterministic model has analysed the Day-ahead Nord Pool Spot data available from 2001 to end of 2014 for Denmark, Norway, Finland, Sweden, Estonia, Latvia and Lithuania. It computes these data with hourly outside temperature series of one unique weather station (Malmö) into a theoretical household. The model enables to get load profiles and annual energy bill. The dweller welfare modification is finally shortly analysed and a payback analysis is provided based on simulated bills and a benchmark of the Smart Thermostat available on the market. The main outcome of the study is that the profitability for the end-user of RTP adoption is highly dependent of the national power market context.

INTRODUCTION

The large diffusion of ICT technologies into domestic housings affords new possibilities of end-users services, centered on the Connected Home. The concept of the Internet of Things (#IoT) gives a new look to the old-fashioned concept of home automation would have never really convinced the dwellers over the last decades. Even though the success of the Connected Home is still not guarantee, the ease of use of smartphones and the reduction of the communication cost increases its chance of success.

Among the portfolio of #IoT devices, the present paper expects to look at load controllers dedicated for space heating control. These ones are now usually commercialized under the designation of Smart Thermostats.

Basically, a thermostat is a device which controls the heating system by sending it ON/OFF set points thanks to a steady-state relay which is driven by a temperature sensor and eventually a schedule or a presence sensor. On top of these initial components, a Smart Thermostat embeds as well computing capabilities in a controller and a communication channel. The addition of a current sensor to such Smart Thermostat enables to monitor as well the heaters power consumption. The embedment of

this functionality leads to switch to connected devices also known as Energy Boxes.

For the objective of optimized space heating, the availability of a communication channel could first enable to receive dynamic power tariff information from the retailers, like Real Time Price (RTP). It enables then to get outside temperature forecast. Such information, associated with heaters power consumption and indoor temperature historic enable to compute the thermal characteristic of the accommodation. From there, it makes possible to forecast accurately the hourly heat load required to comply with an indoor temperature set point over several hours.

The core idea of the present paper is so to assess the added value for an end-user heated by electric heaters, to dispose of these functionalities by replacing its basic thermostat by a Smart Thermostat. The questions asked are finally:

- Is such investment willing to reduce its energy bill?
- What would be the pay-back of such investment?
- Are there any other success conditions to consider, like the power market context?

SIMULATION MODEL

To answer these questions a specific hourly-based deterministic model has been developed. It assesses the profitability of domestic end-users flexibility, enabled by Energy Boxes commissioning. The object used for the simulation is a theoretical domestic household where the electric heaters are controlled by a power-monitored Smart Thermostat, i.e. an Energy Box. The model assumes a perfect knowledge of the outside temperature, power market prices and the thermal characteristics of the household. In such a way the result obtained are the ideal ones. Fig. 1 provides a global view of the system simulated.

Figure 1: Global view of the simulated system Simulation model

Model of the Household

The modeled household [6] is a standard Swedish household located around Malmö (Sweden). It is heated day and night at least at 21°C by electric heaters. The heating system has a nominal power of 6kW/household. The decision not to consider a night cooling-off in the simulation has been inspired by open discussions with end-users consumption experts from *Vattenfall Market Analysis and Future Power System* team that occurred in 2012. Moreover, all of these heaters are already connected to a central thermostat through local connectivity. This is a key restriction to keep in mind.

The heating season for which heat costs are calculated is considered per civil year and leads from Jan 1st to Apr 30nd and from Oct 1st to Dec 31st, i.e. 5064 hours long.

The household is characterized by two thermal coefficients: λ , its global heat losses coefficient (in W/°C) and τ , its thermal constant (in hr). λ corresponds to the mean heat losses coefficient of Southern Sweden households, and has been calculated (1) by considering the mean annual power consumption used in 2010 for electric heating in the households surrounding Malmö ([1], table 3.34) divided by the Heating degree days of the area. The value of degree days has been calculated by summing the difference between an inside set temperature of 21°C and the outside daily temperature of Malmö in 2010 for each day of the heating season. The value chosen for τ (150hr¹) corresponds to a time constant of concrete-built households [2].

Data sets

The hourly Spot price and volume data of Denmark, Norway, Finland, Sweden, Estonia, Latvia and Lithuania have been used for the simulations [3]. In the countries where the Spot markets are split in several prices area, only the ones where the prices are the cheapest and the most expensive have been considered. The bidding areas considered are listed in Table 1. These Spot data have been matched with one unique set of outside temperature: the hourly temperatures measured in Malmö [4].

The period of study leads from 2001 to 2014. The choice to test the market data of several countries on the same thermal system has been motivated by the wish to assess the impact of the market framework on the Energy Box profitability.

End-user tariff definition

The end-user tariffs applied to the model include only the part of the tariff related to power production. Thus it does not include the transmission and distribution taxes neither the public authorities taxes. Two tariffs are used. First, the Real Time Price (RTP) tariff which is strictly equal to the Day-ahead Spot prices. Then the Fix tariff,

which correspond to the mean Day-ahead Spot prices, pondered by the turnover over the year. This Fix tariff has been calculated for each year according to the equation (2). Such Fix tariff aimed to represent the mean cost of power production regardless its time of production. These annual fix prices are displayed in Table 1.

For simplification issues, the hourly spot price taken for the countries split into several bidding area (Denmark, Norway, Sweden), is the average of the price in application in each of the bidding area, regardless the turnover per price area. Equation (3) presents the method of computation.

Moreover, it is assumed that the market penetration of RTP tariff for domestic consumers stays marginal, so that Smart Thermostat spreading is not willing to modify the Day-ahead market level of prices and profiles.

$$(1) \lambda = \frac{\text{Annual mean household heating load (16.9MWh/hous.)}}{24 \times \sum_{d \in [1,120] \cup [273,365]} (21^\circ\text{C} - \min(T_{\text{out}}(d), 21^\circ\text{C}))}$$

$$(2) \text{fixPrice}(j) = \frac{\sum_{h=1}^{8760} \text{SpotPrice}(h,j) * \text{SpotVolume}(h,j)}{\sum_{h=1}^{8760} \text{SpotVolume}(h,j)}$$

$\forall j = 2001 \dots 2014$

$$(3) \text{SpotPrice}(h,j) = \frac{\sum_{n=1}^{nbBiddingArea} \text{SpotPrice}(h,j,n)}{nbBiddingArea}$$

$\forall h = 1 \dots 8760\text{hr}, \forall j = 2001 \dots 2014$

Table 1. Fix tariff (in €/MWh) assumed from 2001 to 2014 in current currency values

Civil years	Denmark		Norway		Sweden		Finland	Estonia	Latvia	Lithuania
	West	East	Kristiansand	Trondheim	Malmö	Lulea				
2001	24.6	24.6			23.5	23.5	23.3			
2002	28.8	28.8	28.7	28.7	29.5	29.5	28.8			
2003	37.1	37.1	38.7	38.7	38.6	38.6	37.0			
2004	29.2	29.2	29.2	29.2	28.3	28.3	27.8			
2005	37.2	37.2	29.4	29.4	30.1	30.1	30.9			
2006	48.0	48.0	48.4	48.4	47.8	47.8	48.8			
2007	34.9	34.9	29.3	29.3	31.4	31.4	30.7			
2008	58.4	58.4	45.0	45.0	50.8	50.8	50.8			
2009	39.7	39.7	35.8	35.8	38.3	38.3	37.9			
2010	54.7	54.7	57.5	57.5	61.3	61.3	59.9			
2011	50.5	50.5	48.6	48.6	49.8	49.8	50.9			
2012	39.2	39.2	32.4	32.4	34.7	34.7	38.5	40.9		
2013	40.7	40.7	39.0	39.0	40.4	40.4	41.9	44.2		50.7
2014	32.4	32.4	29.8	29.8	32.0	32.0	36.5	38.6	52.2	52.5

Energy Box algorithm

The Energy Box willing to be installed in the household modeled (Fig. 1) can control the hourly heat load depending on two different programs. The first program *Prog. 1* aims at minimizing the power consumption, exactly as a conventional thermostat do. Its objective function (4) represents the total power consumption over a period of H hours:

$$(4) \sum_{h=1}^H P(h)$$

The second program *Prog. 2* is close to an ideal algorithm that could be embedded into a power-monitored Smart Thermostat. It leads on an optimization supposed to determine at the beginning of each hour the ideal couples $\{P(h), Tin(h)\}$, willing to minimize the objective function (5). The objective function (5) represents the total heat cost for the three coming days:

¹ It has been noticed during the simulation that τ does not affect the results on a significant manner for any values contained in a range [75;150hr]

$$(5) \sum_{h=1}^{72} Price(h) \cdot P(h)$$

Both *Prog. 1* and *Prog. 2* optimizations must respect the constraints:

$$(6) \begin{cases} T_{min} < T_{in}(h) < T_{max} \\ 0 < P(h) < P_{max} \end{cases} \forall h = 1 \dots 72 \text{ (Fig. 1)}$$

Equation (7) displays finally the relation used by both *Prog.1* and *Prog. 2* to determine the evolution of the inside temperature T_{in} over the hours [2]. It depends on the outside temperature T_{out} , the household's thermal characteristics (λ , τ) and the hourly heat load P :

$$(7) T_{in}(h+1) = T_{in}(h) \cdot e^{-\frac{1}{\tau}} + \left(1 - e^{-\frac{1}{\tau}}\right) \cdot \left(T_{out}(h) + \frac{P(h)}{\lambda}\right)$$

Prog. 2 performs its optimization thanks a linear solver from Matlab ®: Linprog. The model assumes that the communication channel enables the Energy Box which operates *Prog. 2* to get exact three days-ahead forecast of the future hourly outside temperature and end-user prices.

Scenario implemented

Two scenarios have finally been compared to assess the cost savings on the energy bill.

Scenario 1 (Sce 1)

In the first scenario, the Energy Box behaves as a conventional thermostat. It computes the algorithm *Prog. 1*. It assumes that the end-user can subscribe to either an RTP or a Fix tariff. Theoretically, a dweller cannot know which tariff will be the cheapest one for him in the future. It is consequently assumed that the dweller make is opinion on it over years. In order the respect such realism, the model assumes the dweller subscribe per five years periods to the tariff which is the cheapest one for him during this timeframe.

Scenario 2 (Sce 2)

In the second scenario, the Energy Box behaves as a Smart Thermostat. It computes the algorithm *Prog. 2*. In this case, the end-user subscribes so exclusively to the RTP tariff.

RESULTS

Hourly load and temperature profile modification due to cost-driven algorithm use

Fig. 2 illustrates then the impact of the cost-driven strategy on heat load profile and inside temperature variation. It can be noticed the load shifting event occurs permanently, leading to periodic overheating of up to 1°C during these not so cold days (mean outside temperature of 1.5°C).

Benefit of the Smart Thermostat

Global Trend

Fig. 3 presents through blue bars the end user power bill evolutions enabled by the switch from Sce 1 to Sce 2. The evolution is plotted per country from 2001 to 2014.

Figure 2. Impact of the heating scenario on the household load profile and inside temperature variation. Example with Denmark East market data (1st to 3rd February 2011. Daily outside temperature of 1.5°C)

Figure 3. Evolution of the power bill engendered by implementation of Sce 2, compared with Smart Thermostat investment cost assumption in the Scandinavian and Baltic countries (same outdoor reference temperature from Malmö).

The orange vertical lines represent the commissioning year of bidding areas, in the countries concerned. The grey frames surround finally the annualized cost assumption for Energy Box investment (cf. **Pay-back evaluation**, Table 4). The numerical values are displayed in Table 2. Table 3 displays then the baseline tax-free power purchase bill, got with Sce 1 simulations, i.e. without Smart Thermostat.

The first observation that can be made by looking at Fig. 3 is the disparity of incomes from one country to the other, despite simulation performed from the same temperature data sets. It highlights surprisingly the importance of the power market context.

Scandinavian countries

The large presence of positive bars on Fig.3 illustrates stability over the years and a potential profitability of the business model in Denmark, regardless the bidding area. Put aside 2010, Finland benefits more or less of a similar situation, despite less profitable. On the contrary Swedish prognosis stays guarded, while Norway is definitely not a country where end-users should which to RTP tariff. On the whole, not so much differences have been observed between two different bidding areas of the same country.

Baltic Countries

In the Baltic, the situation seems much more profitable, notably due to higher mean Spot prices. The power prices and turnovers historic which are available for these countries are not so extensive yet compared to the data available for Scandinavia. Consequently it is not so easy to stand for a recommendation for the future. Some geopolitics concerns like Russian proximity and early

2015 Crude Oil prices collapse should perhaps be considered as well. But anyway the three years of data available for Estonia steers toward stable perspectives at short term.

Table 2. Annual heating bill variation by switching from Sce1 to Sce 2 in current currency values

Civil years	Denmark		Norway		Sweden		Finland	Estonia	Latvia	Lituania
	West	East	Kristian-sand	Trond-heim	Malmo	Lulea				
2001	37.6	29.0	-	-	19.0	19.0	16.1	-	-	-
2002	52.3	-64.1	-68.3	-61.4	-51.0	-51.0	-41.2	-	-	-
2003	48.9	-34.4	-43.4	-21.2	-15.6	-15.6	-16.9	-	-	-
2004	31.3	36.1	12.0	17.9	24.2	24.2	22.5	-	-	-
2005	61.6	87.5	11.0	13.0	19.8	19.8	26.1	-	-	-
2006	63.8	80.4	12.0	39.4	28.2	28.2	42.4	-	-	-
2007	90.6	74.3	10.2	-37.2	22.4	22.4	25.5	-	-	-
2008	73.8	78.4	9.2	16.2	34.0	34.0	34.6	-	-	-
2009	44.5	70.9	11.6	-11.6	35.9	35.9	36.2	-	-	-
2010	66.8	-116.6	34.6	-134.0	-57.8	-57.8	-65.3	-	-	-
2011	65.1	83.2	-37.9	-32.2	-17.9	-13.5	7.2	-	-	-
2012	67.7	48.8	-34.6	-49.6	-27.0	-16.4	6.4	61.1	-	-
2013	57.9	55.9	-12.8	-10.7	14.3	17.1	34.5	50.7	-	70.0
2014	52.6	58.7	17.8	-0.9	35.8	37.7	67.5	68.7	103.9	104.1

Table 3. Baseline annual heating bill with Sce1 in current currency values

Civil years	Denmark		Norway		Sweden		Finland	Estonia	Latvia	Lituania
	West	East	Kristian-sand	Trond-heim	Malmo	Lulea				
2001	331	333	-	-	319	319	315	-	-	-
2002	374	380	379	379	390	390	380	-	-	-
2003	494	508	529	529	527	527	505	-	-	-
2004	356	382	382	382	370	370	364	-	-	-
2005	459*	496*	388	391	401	401	409	-	-	-
2006	574*	650*	605	630	595	595	613	-	-	-
2007	443*	448*	408	358	417	417	410	-	-	-
2008	610*	613*	491	547	556	556	554	-	-	-
2009	486*	561*	475	469	518	518	516	-	-	-
2010	727	819	862	862	919	919	897	-	-	-
2011	620	644	619	619	634	634	648	-	-	-
2012	534	528	437	437	468	468	519	574	-	-
2013	541	561	537	537	557	557	578	593	-	648
2014	350	379	348	348	374	374	427	431	545	545

* Grey cases: The end-user subscribes to RTP tariff for the Scenario 1.

Model validation

The results obtained have been compared to three authors who have performed close studies. The exact comparison is not so easily doable given that the exact basis (furniture, grid access cost, taxes, etc.) assumed for the baseline heating cost is not specifically. It enables however to confirm the trend.

[8] assessed that RTP adoption would have engendered 35€ of annual savings during Swedish 2005-2006 winter, while the present model assessed saving of 28.2€ (Tab. 2).

[9] announced 10% of savings during the half coldest – so the most benefic half – part of Finish winter 2006, while a value of 6.7% over the whole winter has been obtained with Sce 2.

[10] announced finally a global saving of up to 9.6% for different set of Danish load, while Sce 2 proposed a mean savings of 9.8% from 2001 to 2009 regardless the bidding area.

Pay-back evaluation

The second main answer to provide concerns the

effective payback of a Smart Thermostat.

Benchmark of existing Smart Thermostats

This evaluation has been preceded by a benchmark of the connected devices available on the market, in term of cost and functionalities. As remind, these devices must embed sufficient computation capabilities, an inside temperature sensor, a steady-state relay and a current sensor.

Common Smart Thermostats like Qivivo, Netatmo or Nest embeds all of these functionalities excepted the current sensor. On the contrary the domestic load controller of aggregators [5] embeds this functionality for a while. Last but not least, the space heating optimization process is operated with time constant close to the one of the hourly Spot markets. For such use, it can be assessed that the end user internet connection can be shared for free with the Smart Thermostat. So no communication channel costs are presently assumed, contrary to what has been done in 2012 in [6].

As a result the targeted hardware price of a compliant Smart Thermostat can be simply assessed as the mid-price between the cheapest Smart Thermostat found on the market – Qivivo – and a common aggregator load controller [5]. Such assessment enables to include the over-cost engendered by the addition of a current sensor to the Smart Thermostat. Two levels of prices, depending if the end-user outsources or not the device installation. The outcome is displayed in Table 4. It has been chosen not to not actualized over the years the end-user annual cost, given that the result of Fig. 3 in current currency values does not present any trend of savings rising.

Table 4. Investment cost in a power-monitored Smart Thermostat, in current currency value for 2014.

Cost assumption:	Qivivo [7] (2014)	Cost without installation	Cost with installation	Voltalis [5] (2010, act. at 7.25%)
Hardware costs	100€	160€	160€	219€
Installation costs	80€	0€	120€	120€
Device lifetime	6 years			
End-user cost (in €/home/a)**	30.0€	26.7€	46.7€	90.4€

** actualization rate of 0%

Payback achievability per country

The comparison of Tables 2 and 4 (represented in Fig. 3 as well) shows that Denmark appears finally as the only Scandinavian country where the Smart Thermostat would be paid back within its lifetime. On the contrary, any Baltic countries appears as a suitable location for power-monitored Smart Thermostat use at the condition the assumption of free internet connection access stays true.

Moreover, it has to be remind that this profitability analysis applies for accommodation which already has a concentration of each individual heater command at one unique point. The application of the present bill savings outcomes on a non-equipped household would not be accurate for two reasons. Firstly, the hardware cost and installation cost would be much higher than presently estimated. Secondly, in such a case the first challenge of

home automation will be the household energy efficiency, for which much more incomes can be expected, compared to a simple involvement on the power markets for dynamic tariff subscription.

RESULTS PRECAUTION

Two main precautions must be taken on the results obtained, not to over-assessed the potential of RTP tariff spreading in Northern Europe and Baltics. It concerns first the potential impact of RTP on energy efficiency and dweller welfare. It concerns then the trend of the profile.

Impact of Cost driven strategies on Energy Efficiency and dweller welfare

The basic principle of a cost-driven heating strategy is to use the accommodation inertia as a thermal storage unit, in order to perform load shifting from high prices to low prices periods. The first consequence is a periodic heating over the reference temperature to compensate the household cooling-off during the periods where the heaters are off (Fig. 2). Such over-heating is willing to modify the dweller welfare. The second consequence is an increase of thermal losses due to a larger temperature difference between inside and outside. This rise of losses has to be considered given that it engenders an overconsumption, willing to reduce the building energy efficiency. Such welfare modification and energy efficiency degradation could become large brake for the present business model if we are not well popularized towards end-users or Energy Services Companies (ESCO). Last but not least, Table 2 presents only the savings on the power purchase, while the final all-included bill is composed of taxes proportional to the power consumption. It appears so a risk of savings smoothing that should be considered country per country. Table 5 provides so some clues regarding the overconsumption engendered by the application of the cost-driven heating strategy of Sce 2 in Eastern Denmark. It can be seen that this overconsumption stays relatively contained despite an overheating limit of +2°C. Table 6 provides then the example of the inside temperature dispersion with the application of Sce2 in still Eastern Denmark. The overheating is of at most 0.4°C 62% of the time, and an overheating of more than 1°C is observed 6% of the time only, that stays relatively contains as well.

Table 5: Annual Overconsumption in % engendered by the application of a cost-driven strategies (Sce 2) compared to an energy-optimized strategy, simulated for Denmark East.

2001	2002	2003	2004	2005	2006	2007
1.3%	0.9%	0.9%	1.2%	1.2%	1.8%	1.7%
2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014
1.8%	1.4%	1.0%	2.2%	2.0%	1.7%	1.6%

Table 6: Repartition in % of the inside temperature measured with the application of a cost-driven strategies (Sce 2). Denmark East simulation from 2001 to 2014.

[21;21.2]	[21.2;21.4]	[21.4;21.6]	[21.6;21.8]	[21.8;22.0]	[22;23]
43%	19%	14%	10%	6%	6%

CONCLUSION AND PERSPECTIVES

The study has shown that a business model willing to optimize the domestic end-user heating load curve depending on day-ahead RTP tariff would be profitable in some locations, despite investment in simplified Energy Boxes. The geographical disparity of the results has been the largest surprise of the study, while meantime the bidding area frontier within a given country does not impact the results on a significant manner.

Before going ahead, an analysis on the power market data appears as a mid-term necessity to better understand the origin of the results of the present study. A second interrogation concerns the impact that a large market penetration of RTP tariff would have on the business model presented here. A large penetration would for sure modify the wholesale price profiles, that has not been assumed in the present paper.

Moreover, it is remind that the present study would not be accurate alone to assess the profitability of Energy Box commissioning in accommodations devoid of central thermostat. For these accommodations, the first lever of savings to look at, stays anyway the energy efficiency.

This study provides finally new value assessments regarding the involvement of Demand Response (DR) into already opened power market. It completes outcomes of [6], which assessed the value of household aggregation on the Swedish Balancing Market.

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